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Traumatic Brain Injury in Children, Multidisciplinary Approach – Case Report

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BACKGROUND: Traumatic brain injuries are among the most common causes of acquired disability in children. Because of its complexity, they require an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach in treatment.

AIM: The main aim is to analyze the process of rehabilitation after traumatic brain injury and the importance of multidisciplinary follow up.

METHOD: In this report we analyzed the process of rehabilitation in a patient who was hospitalized in the Institute of Child and Youth Health Care of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia after suffering traumatic brain injury. His medical record was used for acquiring the following information: age, gender, duration of rehabilitation treatment and type of physical therapy modalities used in the rehabilitation treatment.

RESULTS: In the period of 18.08. to 06.11.2017. (81 days) an 16.5-year-old boy was hospitalized for treatment and rehabilitation. Early rehabilitation treatment had started on the 14th day of hospitalization in the Clinic for intensive care and children's surgery. The mechanism of injury was unknown, presumably falling from height. On admission to the hospital he was unresponsive, with periorbital haematoma, bilateral otorrhagia and dilated pupils. CT scan of the head showed epidural haematoma localized temporo-occipital on the right side and fractures of the base of the skull. At the initial examination of the physiatrist the patient was in the passive supination position, unresponsive to pain stimulus, with present initial flexion movement in the left knee and elbow joint, knee joints were extended and hip joints were in external rotation. Barthel index was 0. On the 25th day of hospitalization the patient was relocated to the Clinic for children's habilitation and rehabilitation. An anti-decubitus program was conducted, so was positioning, kinesitherapy, electrotherapy and occupational therapy with multidisciplinary follow up. Upon discharge from the hospital the patient was able to walk independently, with a discreetly disturbed walking pattern in terms of hemiparetic type of walk on the left side, gross muscle strength of the lower extremities had improved and the patient was independent in daily life activities with Barthel index 100.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION: Craniocerebral injuries in children represent a significant medical problem because of their complicated and uncertain course and outcome, with possible consequences and the need for long term rehabilitation. The rehabilitation process of this patient included a multidisciplinary team with implementation of kinesitherapy and other physical modalities. The patient should have firm support from its family and community, in order to go through the rehabilitation process and reintegration in the community with ease.

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